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Abstract

The introduction of microfinance bank has made possible effective mobilization of resources which are channeled into productive investment, thereby enhancing the growth of Small Medium Enterprise and for the development of the economy. Parts of the resources are used as loans and credits to the poor to advance their agricultural and commercial ventures. These credits loans have increased rural output, rural income and employment opportunities. To a considerable extent Micro Finance Banking services have reduced the problem of rural-urban migration by providing gainful employment opportunities for job seekers.

It is our submission that microfinance banking programme in Nigeria has had positive impact on the development of the economy.

The objective of this paper is to provide an overview of microfinance in Nigeria and highlights its problems and prospects. It also reviews some country experiences and suggests strategies for enhancing microfinance as a tool for overall economic development of the country.

Introduction

Microfinance has been defined as a development tool used to create access for the economically active poor to financial services at a sustainably affordable price. The economically active poor are either micro entrepreneurs who operate in the informal sector

(trading, farming, hiring of tools, machinery and equipment, food catering) or people earning wages. Such poor people earn their living in either rural or urban areas.

The financial services for which access is sought are mainly savings and loans. It is estimated that in the developing countries financial services are not available to about 90% of the population and these are the people that microfinance tries to reach.

The providers of microfinance can be categorized into; formal, informal and semi-formal. Moneylenders, traders, pre-financers, producers or suppliers of good and services on credit, friends and family members are informal microfinance providers. The semi-formal providers are credit unions and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). Banks constitute the formal providers of microfinance. The semiformal and the formal are institutional providers. They are referred to as Microfinance Institutions (MFIs).

One of the goals of MFI is social development of the poor. To achieve this, MFIs try to reach as many poor people as possible, going further below the poverty line. Thus, outreach has been the missionary goal of microfinance. This social development goal creates improvement in access to schooling, health facilities and better nutrition. It also empowers the otherwise voiceless. The other goal, which is economic, is to provide a sustainable service. The critical role of sustainability is the ability of the MFI to provide the financial services to the poor continuously over time. Otherwise any welfare gain may roll back making the poor even poorer. Sustainability implies that the MFI is able to cover its costs with revenue earned from its operations. To be sustainable therefore MFIs must apply commercial principles to their activities. This means that microfinance is a commercial business rather than a welfare operation. If microfinance is a commercial business, then it must show profit or surplus income at the bottom of the income statement. The surplus income would enable the MFIs expand their business.

A review of Microfinance experience in Nigeria

The inability of the formal financial institutions to provide financial services to both the urban and rural poor, coupled with the non-sustainability of government sponsored

development-financial schemes, induced the growth of private sector-led microfinance in Nigeria.

Microfinance institutions in Nigeria provide services to both the urban and rural poor and finance micro enterprises. A central bank of Nigeria survey (2001) indicated that the operations of private sector led formal microfinance institutions are relatively new, as most of them were registered after 1981. They operate in both urban and rural areas. The bulk of MFIs client in Nigeria are women. Many private sectors led MFIs began as NGOs established for the promotion of women's rights. Apart from the general belief that women are marginalized in terms of economic opportunities and should have separate promotional agenda, the MFIs are of the view that women perform better than men in managing meager resources and promoting micro enterprises.

Unlike in the banks, asset based collateral is de-emphasized. MFIs also concentrate on short term financing, owing perhaps to the short term nature of their funding sources. The bulk of their financing is on trading activities and 14.1 percent of the total funding are for farming activities while only 3.5 percent was put into manufacturing (Anyanwu 2004).

Credit to the service sector was very minimal, while there was no consumption loan at all. It must be noted that lending is done on group basis where the collateral is the collective pledge of the group to repay based on community recognition.

Above all, the beneficiaries were all low income individuals, operating micro enterprises, indicating that the poor are really at the heart of micro finance in Nigeria. The seemingly disproportionate coverage of commerce in MFI activities is attributed to the quick and high returns that come from investments in the sector, compared with the long gestation periods and lower returns that are associated with the agricultural and manufacturing sectors. Private sector led MFIs in Nigeria depend substantially on aids and grants, which come mainly from abroad. On the average, about 51.0 percent of their operations are funded from this source, while 20.9 0.9 and 1.9 percents were sourced from mobilized savings, owners' capital and bank loans respectively. The balance was made up from unidentified sources.

Prior to the emergency of formal microfinance institutions, informal microfinance activities flourished all over the country. This microfinance arrangement operated and still operates under different names: "esusu" among the Yorubas of Western Nigeria, 'itutu' for the Igbos in the East and 'adashi' in the North for the Hausas. Modern formalized microfinance now operates side by side with the informal services.

The past approach to economic development in Nigeria relied heavily on government intervention in virtually all sectors of the economy, including the financial sectors. Thus, in the bid to provide access to investible funds to induce output growth for improvement in living standards in the country, specialized financial institutions were established by government since 1960 a brief appraisal of the institutions created and policy measures evolved by government to provide financial services to the poor in the past are outlined below:

Development Finance Institutions and Microfinance in Nigeria

Development finance institutions (DFI) were established to contribute to the growth of specific sectors of the economy and could provide an additional source of funding to the MFIs. This could be done on on-lending basis, instead of the current practice of dealing directly with micro enterprise owners, using the latter as an intermediary would be more efficient because MFIs have greater expertise in financing smaller intermediaries. Each DFI was designed with the function of promoting the development of a specific sector or sub-sector (CBN, 2000). They include;

- a. The Nigerian Industrial Development Bank (NIDB): was established in 1964 and charged with the function of harnessing both local and foreign skills and private capital in the development of new industries and expansion of existing ones.
- b. The Nigerian Bank for Commerce and Industry (NBCI): established in 1973 in order to provide equity capital and funds to small and medium scale enterprises.
- c. The Nigerian Agricultural and Cooperative Bank: this institution was also established in 1973 and was of more relevance to micro enterprises. It was designed

to assist financing of agricultural projects thereby enhancing the level and quality of agricultural production. or)

- d. The Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria: established in 1977 with the mandate to provide funding for residential and other housing needs of individuals and corporate organizations

Other Financial Institutions

- a. Peoples Bank of Nigeria (PBN): established by the Federal government in 1988 with an initial take-off grant of N30 million to meet the credit needs of small borrowers who were unable to satisfy the stringent collateral requirements demanded by conventional banks. The bank was designed to cater for the credit needs of informal sector operators such as artisans and petty traders in both the urban and rural areas, and was expected to facilitate access to credit for economic operators at the grassroots and thereby increase their self-reliance. The PBN continued to depend on government subventions for its operations. Since this was not sustainable, it was subsequently merged with the NACB in 2000 for better performance.
- b. **Community Banks:** these are self-sustaining financial institutions owned and managed by local communities such as community development associations, town unions, co-operative societies, farmers' groups, social clubs, etc. to provide financial services to the respective communities. They are to promote rural development and enhance economic growth and development at the grassroots' level. Their activities complement those of rural bank branches and branches of the PBN. They accept deposits, provide ancillary banking services, invest their funds in various money market instruments and provide credit facilities to their customers. The deposit and lending rates of the CBs are lower than those of commercial banks.

Special Schemes and Funds

Special schemes and funds were also created to facilitate access to credit for microfinance activities nationwide. Among these were the Family Economic Advancement Programme (FEAP), National Directorate of Employment (NDE) program and the small and medium scale enterprises (SMEES)

(a) Family Economic Advancement Programme: this was a micro credit scheme program aimed at stimulating appropriate economic activities at the grass roots level through establishment of cottage industries and creating avenues for the people to earn higher incomes. It was established by the government in 1988 in reaction to the increasing levels of poverty occasioned by the implementation of the structural adjustment policies. The main objectives of this program include:

- Provision of loans directly to people at the ward level in order to enable them establish small-scale industries;
- Provision of employment opportunities at the lowest levels;
- Improve standards of living;
- Encouragement of producers at the lower levels to form cooperative societies through which to promote development consciousness; ancillary banking services, invest their funds in various money market instruments and provide credit facilities to their customers. The deposit and lending rates of the CBs are lower than those of commercial banks.

The distress in the financial sector in the mid-1990s led to the entrapment of N500 million in the bank. Other problems that the community banks face include incompetent board and management, poor record keeping, insufficient assets to meet obligations and inadequate earnings. In order to address the developments in the economy which called for sufficiently higher capital to absorb and cushion risks associated with doing business in the sub-sectors, community banks were directed to raise their capital base from N3 million to N5 million or before August 31, 2001.

Policy Strategies

- i. A number of strategies have been derived from the objectives and targets as follows:

- ii. License and regulate the establishment of Microfinance Banks (MFBs)
- iii. Promote the establishment of NGO-based microfinance institutions
- iv. Promote the participation of Government in the microfinance industry by encouraging States and Local Governments to devote at least one percent of their annual budgets to micro credit initiatives administered through MFBs.
- v. Promote the establishment of institutions that support the development and growth of microfinance service providers and clients;
- vi. Strengthen the regulatory and supervisory framework for MFBs;
- vii. Promote sound microfinance practice by advocating professionalism, transparency and good governance in microfinance institutions;
- viii. Mobilize domestic savings and promote the banking culture among low-income groups;
- ix. Strengthen the capital base of the existing microfinance institutions;
- x. Broaden the scope of activities of microfinance institutions;
- xi. Strengthen the skills of regulators, operators, and beneficiaries of microfinance initiatives;
- xii. Clearly define stakeholders' roles in the development of the microfinance sub-sector; and Collaborate with donors, coordinate and monitor donor assistance in microfinance in line with the provisions of this policy.

Appraisal of Microfinance Banks in Nigeria

The establishment of microfinance banks has become imperative to serve the following purposes:

- i. Provide diversified, affordable and dependable financial services to the active poor, in a timely and competitive manner, that would enable them to undertake and develop long-term, sustainable entrepreneurial activities;
- ii. Mobilize savings for intermediation;

- iii. Create employment opportunities and increase the productivity of the active poor in the country, thereby increasing their individual household income and uplifting their standard of living.
- iv. Enhance organized, systematic and focused participation of the poor in the socio-economic development and resource allocation process;
- v. Provide veritable avenues for the administration of the micro credit programmes of government and high net worth individuals on a non-recourse basis. In particular, this policy ensures that state governments shall dedicate an amount of not less than 1% of their annual budgets for the on-lending activities of microfinance banks in favour of their residents; and
- vi. Render payment services, such as salaries, gratitude, and pension for various tiers of government:

Policy Measures and Instruments for the Establishment of Microfinance Banks

Private sector-driven microfinance banks shall be established. The banks shall be required to be well-capitalized, technically sound, and oriented towards lending, based on the cash flow, and character of clients, There shall be two categories of Micro finance Banks (MFBs), namely:

- i. Micro Finance Banks (MFBs) licensed to operate as a unit bank, and
- ii. Micro Finance Banks (MFBs) licensed to operate in a state.

The recognition of these two categories of banks does not preclude them from aspiring to having a national coverage, subject to their meeting the prudential, requirements. This is to ensure an orderly spread and coverage of the market and to avoid, in particular, concentration in areas already having large numbers of financial institutions.

An existing NGO which intends to operate an MFB can either incorporate a subsidiary MFB, while still carrying out its NGO operations, or fully convert into a MFB.

i. MFBs Licensed to Operate as a unit bank a.k.a. Community Banks

MFBs licensed to operate as unit banks shall be community based banks. Such banks can operate branches and/or cash centres subject to meeting the prescribed prudential

requirements and availability of free funds for opening branches/cash centres. The minimum paid-up capital for this category of banks shall be N20.0 million for each branch.

ii. MFBs Licensed to Operate in a State

MFBs licensed to operate in a state shall be authorized to operate in all parts of the State (or the Federal Capital Territory) in which they are registered, subject to meeting the prescribed prudential requirements and availability of free funds for opening branches. The minimum paid-up capital for this category of banks shall be N1.0 billion.

Ownership of Microfinance Banks

Microfinance banks can be established by individuals, groups of individuals, community development associations, private corporate entities, or foreign investors. Significant ownership diversification shall be encouraged to enhance good corporate governance of licensed MFBs.

Universal banks that intend to set up any of the two categories of MFB as subsidiaries shall be required to deposit the appropriate minimum paid-up capital and meet the prescribed prudential requirements and if, in the view of the regulatory authorities, have also satisfied all the requirements stipulated in the guidelines, shall be licensed.

No individual, group of individuals, their proxies or corporate entities, and/or their subsidiaries, shall establish more than one MFB under a different or disguised name.

Participation of the Existing Financial Institutions in Microfinance Activities

Universal Banks

Universal banks currently engaged in microfinance services, either as an activity or product and do not wish to set up a subsidiary, shall be required to set up a department /unit for such services and shall be subjected to the provisions of the MFB regulatory and supervisory guidelines.

Community Banks

All licensed community banks, prior to the approval of this policy, shall transform to microfinance banks licensed to operate as a unit bank on meeting the prescribed new capital

and other conversion requirements within a period of 24 months from the date of approval of this policy. Any community bank which fails to meet the new capital requirement within the stipulated period shall cease to operate as a community bank. A community bank can apply to convert to a microfinance bank licensed to operate in a state if it meets the specific capital and other conversion requirements.

Non-Governmental Organization Micro Finance Institutions (NGO MFI's):

This policy recognizes the existence of credit-only, membership-based microfinance institutions which shall not be required to come under the supervisory purview of the Central Bank of Nigeria. Such institutions shall engage in the provision of micro credits to their targeted population and will not mobilize deposits from the general public.

The registered NGO-MFIs shall be required to forward periodic returns on their activities to the CBN. NGO-MFI's that wish to obtain the operating licence of a microfinance bank shall be required to meet the specified provisions as stipulated in the regulatory and supervisory guidelines.

Transformation of the Existing NGO-MFI's

Any existing NGO-MFI's which intends to operate an MFB can either incorporate a subsidiary MF B while still carrying out its NGO operations or fully convert into an MFB. Any NGO-MFI's that wishes to convert fully into a microfinance bank must obtain an operating licence and shall be required to meet the specified provisions as stipulated in the regulatory and supervisory guidelines.

Justification for the Capital Requirements

The present capital base of N5 million for community banks has become too low for effective financial intermediation. Indeed, to set up a community a bank, at least N5 million is required for the basic infrastructure, leaving zero or a negative balance for banking operations.

From a survey of community banks, an operating fund of N50 million is about the minimum capital (own capital and deposits) a community bank needs to provide effective

banking services to its clients. However, it is recognized that since many community banks are based in the rural areas, their promoters may not be able to effectively raise N50 million as shareholders' funds.

Hence, the stipulation of N20 million as shareholders' funds for the unit microfinance banks. The banks are expected to engage in aggressive mobilization of savings from micro-depositors to shore up their operating funds.

A state coverage microfinance bank that would operate multiple branches would be expected to take off with funds sufficient to operate full branch in at least two-thirds of the Local government Areas in that State. Hence, a minimum paid-up capital of N1.0 billion shall be required to obtain the licence to operate a state coverage MFB. Expansion to another states shall be subject to the provision of N1.0 billion minimum shareholders' funds unimpaired by losses, and after opening branches in at least two-thirds of the Local Government Areas of the state it is currently licensed to operate in, and if in the view of the regulatory authorities, it has satisfied all the requirements stipulated in the guidelines. The experience of other countries sheds light on the level of capitalization required for microfinance banks. In most countries, the level of capitalization depends on the geographical coverage of the banks, and for some countries, even for a particular scope of coverage (district or province), the population and volume of business of the area further determine the level of capitalization. The capitalization requirements in other countries levels for the two categories of MFBs in this policy.

The licensing of microfinance banks shall be the responsibility of the Central Bank of Nigeria. A licensed institution shall be required to add "microfinance bank"; after its name. All such names shall be registered with the Corporate Affairs Commission (CAC), in compliance with the Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA) 1990.

Establishment of a National Microfinance Consultative Committee

A National Microfinance Consultative Committee (NMFCC) shall be constituted by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) to provide direction for the implementation and monitoring of this policy. Membership of their Committee shall be determined from time to time by

the CBN. The Microfinance Support Unit of the CBN shall serve as the Secretariat to these Committee.

Credit Reference Bureau

Due to the peculiar characteristics of microfinance practice, a credit reference bureau, which shall provide information on microfinance clients and aid decision making, is desirable. In this regard, the present Credit Risk Management System in the CB shall be expanded to serve the needs of the microfinance sector.

Rating Agency

The CBN shall encourage the establishment of private rating agencies for the sub-sector to rate microfinance institutions, especially those NGO-T MFIs which intend to transform to microfinance banks.

Deposit Insurance Scheme

Since MFBs are deposit-taking institutions and in order to reinforce public confidence in them, MFBs shall qualify for the deposit insurance scheme of the Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC).

Management Certification Process

In order to bridge the technical skills gap, especially among operators of microfinance banks, the policy recognizes the need to set up an appropriate capacity building programme for MFBs. To this end, the CBN shall put in place a microfinance bank management certification process to enhance the acquisition of appropriate microfinance operational skills of the management team of MFBs. A transition period of twenty four (24) months shall be allowed from the date of launching the policy.

Apex Association of Microfinance Institutions

The establishment of an apex association of microfinance institutions to promote uniform standards, transparency, good corporate practices and full disclosures in the conduct of MFI businesses shall be encouraged.

Linkage Programme

The policy recognizes the importance of the provision of wholesale funds for microfinance banks to expand their outreach. Pursuant to this, the CBN shall work out the modalities for

fostering linkages between universal/development banks, specialized finance institutions and the microfinance banks to enable the latter source for wholesale funds and refinancing facilities for on-lending to their clients.

Establishment of a Microfinance Development Fund

In order to promote the development of the sub-sector and provide for the wholesale funding requirements of microfinance banks, a micro finance sector development fund shall be set upon. The fund shall provide necessary support for the development of the sub-sector in terms of refinancing facility, capacity building, and other promotional activities. The fund would be sourced from governments and through soft facilities from the international development financing institutions, as well as multilateral and bilateral development institutions.

Prudential Requirements

The CBN recognizes the peculiarities of microfinance practice and shall accordingly put in place appropriate regulatory and prudential requirements to guide the operations and activities of the microfinance banks.

Disclosure of Sources of Funds

Licensed MFBs shall be required to disclose their sources of funds, in compliance with the Money Laundering Prohibition act 2004.

Corporate governance for Microfinance Banks

The board of directors of MFBs shall be primarily responsible for corporate governance in the microfinance banks. To ensure good governance of the banks, the board of directors shall be responsible for establishing strategic objectives, policies and procedures that would guide and direct the activities of the banks and the means to attain same, as well as the mechanism for monitoring management's performance.

Thus, while management of the day-to-day affairs of the banks shall be the responsibility of the management team, the board of directors shall, however, be responsible for monitoring and overseeing management's actions. Consequently, the licensed microfinance banks shall be expected to operate under a diversified and professional board of directors.

Regulatory Incentives

The new window of opportunity for the emerging microfinance banks in bringing financial services to people who never had access to such services before, would require the support of government and that of regulatory authorities. The CBN shall collaborate with the appropriate fiscal authorities in providing a favourable tax treatment of MFBs' financial transaction, such as exemption from value added tax (VAT) on lending, or tax on interest income or revenue.

Similarly, the principle of exemption from profit tax shall be applied to any MFB that does not distribute its net surplus but ploughs it back and reinvests the surplus to finance more economically beneficial micro, small and medium entrepreneurship. Furthermore, a Rediscounting and Refinancing Facility (RRF) shall be made available to MFBs for purposes of providing liquidity assistance to support and promote microfinance programmes. This would enable MFBs that have met the CBN prudential requirements to, on a sustainable basis, provide and render micro credits and other services to their clients.

Roles and Responsibilities of stakeholders

The roles and responsibilities of stakeholders shall include the following:

Government

Government shall be responsible for:

- i. Ensuring a stable macro-economic environment, providing basic infrastructures (electricity, water, roads, telecommunications, etc), political and social stability;
- ii. Fostering adequate land titling and other property rights sufficient to serve the collateral needs of borrowers and financial institutions;
- iii. Instituting and enforcing donor and foreign aid guidelines on micro-finance institutions to streamline their activities in line with this policy; and
- iv. Setting aside an amount of not less than 1% of the annual budgets of state governments for on-lending activities of microfinance banks in favour of their residents.

Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN)

The role of the CBN shall include the following:

- i. Establishing a national microfinance consultative committee
- ii. Evolving a clear microfinance policy that spells out eligibility and licensing criteria, provides operational/prudential standards and guidelines to all stakeholders;
- iii. Evolving a microfinance sub-sector and institution policies aimed at providing regulatory harmony, promoting healthy competition and mainstreaming microfinancing with formal intermediation;
- iv. Adopting an appropriate regulatory and supervisory framework;
- v. Minimizing regulatory arbitrage through periodic reviews of the policy and guidelines;

- vi. Promoting linkage programmes between universal/development banks, specialized finance institutions and the microfinance banks;
- vii. Continuously advocating market determined interest rates for government-owned institutions and promoting the channeling of government microfinance funds through MFBs; and
- viii. Implementing appropriate training programmes for regulators, promoters and practitioners in the sub-sector, in collaboration with stakeholders.

Micro Finance Banks and Economic Development

Microfinance service providers shall:

- i. Provide efficient and effective financial services, such as credit, deposits, commodity/inventory collateralization, leasing, and innovative transfer/payment services;
- ii. Undertake appropriate recruitment and retention of qualities professionals through transparent and competitive processes;
- iii. Adopt continuous training and capacity building programmes to improve the skills of staff; and
- iv. Strictly observe their fiduciary responsibility, remain transparent and accountable in protecting savers' deposits.
- v. Compliance with the rules and regulations as stipulated by the regulatory authorities.

Public Sector Poverty Alleviation Agencies

The MFB policy recognizes the roles of public sector MFIs and poverty alleviation agencies such as the National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP) in the development of the sub-sector. They shall be encouraged to perform the following functions:

- i. Provision of resources targeted at difficult to reach clients and the poorest of the poor;
- ii. Capacity building;
- iii. Development of MFIs' activities nation-wide;
- iv. Nurturing of new MFIs to a sustainable level; and
- v. Collaborating/partnering with other relevant stakeholders.

Donor Agencies

Donor agencies offer free or subsidized funds, donations or technical assistance for the development of the microfinance industry in Nigeria.

They include bilateral and multilateral institutions, NGOs and missionaries with a pro-poor orientation. The services provided by donor agencies include grants, donation, technical assistance, etc.

The donor agencies, in conducting their microfinance activities, shall comply with the relevant provisions of this policy. The target clients for donors' support may include: MFIs, NGOs, regulators and other relevant agencies. However, for the purpose of leveraging the evolving micro financing initiative, donors are expected to direct most of their assistance to licensed MFBs to ensure an orderly resource injection, transparency and synergy.

There exists a huge untapped potential for financial intermediation at the micro and rural levels of the Nigerian economy. Attempts by government in the past to fill this gap, through supply-driven creation of financing institutions and instruments, have failed, due to the poor capitalization of such schemes and restrictive regulatory and supervisory procedures, among other factors. The community banks were designed to fill the gap, but their low

capital base and isolated mode of operation have not enabled them to make meaningful contributions to micro financing.

Challenges of Microfinance in Nigeria

Over the years, the various specialized financial institutions established by the government have been faced with one problem or the other as such could not meet the objectives for which they were set up. The reasons for their failure include the following:

1. First, because the programmes offered very low interest loans, the volume of funds supplied was limited, and it was impossible for the lending institutions to achieve self-sustainability.
2. Second, lending volume and sustainability were further eroded because these institutions lacked incentive to undertake careful underwriting and enforce timely repayment.
3. Third, state owned programme, particularly those that lack profit incentives, were very vulnerable to political influence. Borrowers were frequently selected for political reasons rather than because they fit the profile of the ostensibly targeted beneficiaries or were sound credit risks.
4. Finally, wealthy households appropriated the benefits of many of these programmes because they preferred to borrow from them rather than from the unsubsidized informal sector. Consequently, the development finance institutions suffered serious erosion of their capital bases and had to be recapitalized for survival.

To commercialize microfinance, the MFIs should aim at up scaling their operations and transforming into regulated financial institutions. On the other hand, the commercial banks also should be downscaling their operation to provide micro financial services.

What then are the issues underpinning MFIs up scaling to commercialize their operations? They are; product development, product pricing, profitability, competition and professionalism. In African entry of commercial banks into microfinance is rare. Where they have been, it has been due to state ownership and mandate. The private commercial banks' lack of motivation is due to a number of factors such as lack of knowledge, transaction and monitoring costs, low interest rate and profitability.

The challenges of the informal microfinance institutions are tied to the peculiar nature of their operations. Their deposits are largely small in size, the velocity of funds mobilization and financial intermediation is high, interest rates are not market-based and often in the formal markets.

In addition, interest on loans is collected upfront and finally, the size of deposit has a high seasonality element. Because of seasonal variations, mobilization of deposits is especially affected in periods of poor harvest.

At such time, there is little to be lent by the operators to promote financial intermediation hence, the volatile nature of deposits.

Lessons of Experience from Indonesia, Ghana and the Philippines Nigeria like Indonesia, Ghana and the Philippines, is a developing country and they all share similar characteristics hence the basis for attempting to draw lessons of experience from these three countries which have made significant progress in the area of MFIs development.

Nigeria like Indonesia has a very large population and with the exception of the Philippines, the other three countries have a gross national income per capital of less than one thousand dollars, while that of Nigeria is the least. Population below the poverty line is high for all these countries ranging from 27.1 percent for Indonesia in 1999 to 36.8 percent for the Philippines in 1997. For Nigeria, it was 34.1 percent in 1992 93 and the situation deteriorated further in the late 1990s. domestic credit provided by the banking sector as a percent of GDP was estimated by the World Bank to be only 12.4 percent for Nigeria in 2000 and as high as 66.2 percent for Indonesia. This is a clear indication of the need to develop microfinance institutions in Nigeria so as to improve the per capital GDP growth rate estimated at 0.4 percent in 1999 2000 for Nigeria compared with 3. 1 percent for Indonesia.

- **The Indonesia Case Study:** The report by Marisol Raviez examined five Indonesia micro finance programmes owned by the central or a local government that currently serves low-income clients in low-density areas. The highlights of their findings are presented below.

i. **Structure of Microfinance Sector in Indonesia**

Under the Badan Kredit Kecamatan (BKK), financial institutions owned by the south Kalimantan provincial government, there are 110 units for its 109 sub-districts and field staff are required to travel to surrounding Villages to transact business. The 34 BKK units created before 1992 make loans and accept deposits while the 76 units created after 1992 only make loans but charge higher interest rates for sustainability. The Lumbung Kredit Pedesaan (LKP) is a system of semi-formal financial institutions owned by the provincial government of Nusa Tenggara Barat (NTB). LKP is very similar in structure and function to BKK.

The program Hubungan Bank dan KSM (PHBK), on the other hand is a micro finance program sponsored by the Central Bank of Indonesia (BI) and the German Government's Agency for Technical Cooperation (GTZ).

The program operates in 10 provinces and had expanded to 3 more, by March 1996, 323 banks or bank branches were participating in this program. The program provides technical assistance to private and state-owned banks, non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and borrower groups to help them develop group lending skills. Client groups can obtain loans and open savings accounts. **The Pembinaan Peningkatan Pendapatan Petani Nelayan Kecil (P4K)** also is a group-based micro enterprise lending and promotion program targeting the rural poor. P4K operates in 6 provinces and expanded on a pilot basis to an additional 12. Ministry of Agriculture extension workers act as agents for the government-owned bank Rakyat Indonesia (BRI) to extend lending and savings services to the rural poor. The program also provides training in micro-enterprise skills, and attempts to link borrower groups with community activities and social service agencies.

Finally, the Badan Credit Desa BKD) is a system of village based financial institutions where units are owned by individual villages and operated by village governments. BKD units are located in the rural areas of Java. There are 5,345 units, of which 4,806 were active in 1996. all units make loans and accept deposits.

ii. Loan characteristics

Loan products vary by institutions but generally carry high interest rates and have short repayment periods. While PHBK and P4K make group loans, LKP and BKD make

individual loans. BKK primarily makes individual loans, although some of its units have begun to make group loans. Nominal effective annualized interest rates ranged from about 24 percent for P4K, to over 400 percent for those PHBK loans that pass through several intermediaries. Most of the programmes' loans have effective annual real (inflation adjusted) interest rates of 50 percent or more. This is much higher than the BRI Unit Desa real interest rate of about 21 percent for prompt payers. The programmes' maximum loan terms vary from 3 to 18 months and loans are paid in weekly/monthly installments. None of the programs requires collateral for small loans.

iii. Outreach and sustainability

On the average loan sizes range from 7 to 13 percent of Indonesia's GDP per capital (US\$67 to US\$130). The ratio for 9 of the world's most respected micro-credit programs is 16 to 136 percent. Women account for 40 to 62 percent of the programmes' borrowers, versus 20 to 90 percent for the internationally respected programs. The programs accept voluntary savings deposits, and have a savings requirement to obtain at least some loans. Savings accounts generally earn interest at a rate approximately equal to the inflation rate. Four of the five programs have experienced rapid growth in the number of loans they have issued in recent years.

Four of the programs had annual default rates of 3 percent or less in 1994 and 1995. this level of default is satisfactory by international micro credit standards. BKK can now operate on a sustainable basis without subsidies. LKP and PHBK have experienced rapidly declining subsidies in recent years. P4K s subsidies increased was significantly lower than in the early 1990s.

b. The Experience of Ghana and the Philippines

Responding to the rapid growth of various types micro-finance institutions (MFIs) around the world and the gap in knowledge on whether and how these institutions should be regulated, a team from the world bank comprising Hennie Van Greuning, Joselito Gallardo and Bikki Randhawa produced a policy research working paper No. 2061 (February 1999) entitled, "A framework for Regulating Microfinance Institutions". The paper sought to

provide a framework for addressing regulatory issues which impact the operations and the institutional development of MFIs.

The two countries selected for this field testing and assessment were Ghana and the Philippines, which have a wide range of informal, semi-formal and formal MFIs providing financial services to the poor, but have legal system and regulatory frameworks which differ in how financial intermediation activities by MFIs are regulated and/or supervised. Subsequent in-depth work on issues in developing sustainable rural/microfinance in Indonesia reviewed earlier presented an opportunity to deepen the assessment of how the legal and regulatory environment is important to sustainable microfinance.

The assessment and comparative analysis carried out focused on the key issues in the legal system and judicial processes, as well as on the regulatory and supervisory environment for microfinance which are being addressed by the governments and microfinance stakeholders in the countries.

Structure of Microfinance Sector in Ghana

Ghana has a tiered range of formal, semi-formal and informal institutions, providing microfinance services to the urban and rural poor and underserved sectors of the economy. Financial intermediation and credit activities are under the regulatory jurisdiction of the bank of Ghana (BOG). The regulatory framework under the Banking Law (1989) and the Non-Bank Financial Institutions (NBFI) Law 1993) accommodate a tiered structure of licensed financial intermediaries and of financial regulation. The risk management criteria consideration by BOG as important for MFIs include: capital adequacy; mandatory liquidity reserves; security for loans; recognition and classification of delinquent loans; provisioning for portfolio at risk; as well as guidelines and standards for writing-off of non-performing loans.

Structure of Microfinance sector in the Philippines

Compared to Ghana, the Philippines has a comparatively wider range of formal, semi-formal and informal institutions providing microfinance services to the urban and rural

poor and underserved sectors of the economy. Financial intermediation and credit activities are under the regulatory jurisdiction of the Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas (BSP). The regulatory framework under the General Banking Law of 2000 (which repealed the General Banking Act of 1949) and a number of parallel Laws governing specialized banks and NBFIs have made room for a tiered structure of licensed financial intermediaries and of financial regulatory.

The General Banking Law of 2000 provides adequate room for banks and quasi-banks to have foreign equity content: foreign individual and nonbank corporations are permitted to own or control up to 40 percent of the voting stock of a licensed bank or quasi-bank. The percentage of foreign-owned voting stock is determined by the citizenship or individual shareholders. Regardless of its place of incorporation. The risk management criteria considered by BSP as important for MFIs include: capital adequacy; solvency standards; mandatory liquidity reserves; security for loans, recognition and classification of delinquent loans; provisioning for portfolio at risk, as well as guidelines and standards for writing-off of non-performing loans.

Lessons for Nigerian Microfinance

From Indonesia, we learn that provision of credit to low-income people with a valuable service at an initial, affordable cost to governments or donors is a necessity as well as the reduction or even elimination of high real interest rates. There is also the need for subsidies, aggressive pursuing of repayments, and achieving a significant volume of business.

MFIs would also be able to obtain strong financial performance through the use of incentives for staff and clients; and clients in remote areas can be reached through sub-district based units and field staff. It is pertinent to note that poorly designed supervision systems, will weaken the system as well as inability to face political pressures that undermine their commitment to sound banking practices.

The Indonesian experience also revealed that the long-term health of MFIs can be promoted by limiting microfinance subsidies. This is achieved by ensuring that microfinance initiatives follow market-based principles which include: (i) instituting accounting and report formats that accurately track all (including in-kind) subsidies and (ii) appropriately provision for bad-debt and depreciate fixed assets. In addition, annual subsidy reduction goals should be set to promote MFIs self-sustenance, particularly for private providers that would subsequently have to generate profits to remain in the market.

Use the tiered regulatory approach to promote development of sustainable microfinance as done in the Philippines and Ghana. by clearly identifying pathways for NGOs and semi-formal MFIs to become legitimate institutions under the regulatory framework with greater ability to access finance resources from commercial markets. E.g. CARD rural bank in the Philippines, Sinapi Aba trust in Ghana. Though all three countries have licensed rural banks, their relative financial performance and sustainability profiles have differed significantly largely because of differences in effective governance by owners/stakeholders and the base of unimpaired capital and ability of owners to step forward with additional capital. This identifies the effectiveness of corporate ownership.

Finally, the adjustment of risk management criteria made by BOG and BSP recognize the special characteristics of microfinance operations and provide useful lessons for regulatory

authorities in other countries like Nigeria. For instance, with respect to capital adequacy standards, the prudential levels set for licensed MFIs by the banking authorities in the Philippines, Indonesia and Ghana do not differ much from the levels set for the larger commercial and thrift banking institutions in those countries.

Global best practice experience of MFIs reporting their operating and financial performance data to the Mirco Banking Bulletin provide clear empirical evidence to support more prudential capital adequacy standards for MFIs.

Conclusion

It is our submission that a robust economic growth cannot be achieved without putting in place well focused programmes to reduce poverty through empowering the people by increasing their access to factors of production, especially credit. The latent capacity of the poor for entrepreneurship would be significantly enhanced through the provision of microfinance services to enable them engage in economic activities and be more self-reliant, increase employment opportunities, enhance household income, and create wealth. Since Microfinance is about providing financial services to the poor who are traditionally not served by the conventional financial institutions.

Micro Finance Banks will serve as a support mechanism for government integrated rural development programmes and the development of Nigerian Economy as a whole.

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